

Enhancing Metacognition with Competence Lists

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Abstract

While the use of desk calculators has diminished mental arithmetic skills, the availability of powerful artificial intelligence further reduces students' motivation to solve mathematical problems. "Why should I do it?" they ask. However, without a solid mathematical foundation, the ability to critically assess AI-generated results is compromised.

The SEFI competency framework provides a strong foundation for undergraduate mathematics courses. The learning objectives outlined in this framework serve as the basis for our three-volume exercise book "Mathe – kann ich". Together with its competency lists, the book offers students a clear understanding of what is expected of them. Furthermore, by engaging with the material, students focus not on their mistakes but on their progress, as they check off problems they have mastered and competencies they have acquired. This approach enhances metacognition and reinforces long-term retention of the material.

The method of bringing SEFI competencies to life through exercises and worked-out solutions has received excellent feedback from undergraduate students in business IT and industrial engineering. This is further reinforced by the lecturers' feedback on students' solutions to voluntarily selected problems.

Introduction

The use of competence lists is a well-established method to support self-organized learning (Schmidt-Gröttrup 2014). According to Herold & Herold (2017), a competence list is a table of competencies defined by learning objective, activity record, taxonomy and a column to check off. Students use competence lists in order to monitor and check whether they have individually reached the targeted learning objective. In maths teaching the solution of exercises whether formative or summative is central. An example of a competence list is given in figure 1 taken from Schmidt-Gröttrup & Risse (2024) chapter 39 on matrices. Instead of a taxonomy, an expected duration for the exercise is given.

Questions to the lecturer

Sensible working with competence lists requires the lesson to be aligned to the learning objectives. This alignment means the lecturer has to make sure, that

- lessons are based on verifiably formulated learning objectives,
- the importance of the learning objectives is communicated to students,
- lessons, exercises and exams are aligned with the learning objectives,
- exercises and exams are aligned.

Nr	Ich kann	Aufgabe	✓
Matrizen: Grundbegriffe			
359	erklären, was mit einer Matrix gemeint ist,	39.1	
360	die grundlegenden mit Matrizen verbundenen Begriffe wiedergeben wie Diagonale, Spur, quadratische und Dreiecks- und Einheitsmatrix,	39.1	
361	die Transponierte einer Matrix bestimmen,	39.4, 39.8	
Matrizen: Arithmetik			
362	eine skalare Multiplikation mit einer Matrix durchführen,	39.4, 39.12, 39.22	
363	erkennen, ob zwei Matrizen addiert werden können, und ggfls. ihre Summe berechnen,	39.4, 39.5, 39.6	
364	erkennen, ob zwei Matrizen multipliziert werden können, und ggfls. ihr Produkt berechnen,	39.2, 39.4, 39.6, 39.7	
365 *	Transformationsmatrizen erkennen und verwenden,	39.7, 39.9	
Determinanten			
366	die Determinanten von 2×2 und 3×3 -Matrizen berechnen,	39.11	
367	die geometrische Bedeutung von 2×2 und 3×3 Determinanten erklären,	39.10, 39.13	
368	die elementaren Eigenschaften einer Determinanten bei ihrer Auswertung benutzen	39.12, 39.14, 39.15, 39.16	
Matrizen: Rang			
369	den Rang einer Matrix berechnen,	39.17, 39.18	
Matrizen: Inverse			
370	die Bedingung an eine quadratische Matrix angeben, damit sie eine Inverse hat,	39.20, 39.21	
371	die Inverse einer 2×2 -Matrix angeben, wenn diese existiert,	39.20, 39.21	
372	die Inverse einer Matrix mit Zeilen-Operationen berechnen, falls sie existiert,	39.22	
373 *	allgemeine Eigenschaften der Invertierung verifizieren.	39.19, 39.21	

Figure 1: Competence List for Chapter 39 in “Mathe - kann ich”

SEFI Curriculum

The curriculum of the SEFI mathematics working group was developed over two decades in a series of seminars and workshops on mathematical education for engineers (Alpers 2014). Its curricular part is divided into four core levels, from Core Zero containing the indispensable basics for any engineering education, to Core 1 containing the basic knowledge for general engineering. Core 2 contains topics that are essential for specific engineering disciplines, and Core 3 contains highly specialized mathematical knowledge for example numerical solution of ordinary differential equations. Within each core, individual topics are organized along five mathematical disciplines, namely algebra, analysis and calculus, discrete mathematics, geometry, statistics and probability. Apart from Core 3, explicit learning objectives are formulated. They are therefore an excellent basis for planning courses using competence lists.

Book Series “Mathe - kann ich”

The learning objectives of Core Level 0 and 1 of the SEFI Curriculum are the basis for the three volumes “Mathe - kann ich” (Schmidt-Gröttrup et al, 2022, 2023, 2024). They contain the basics of algebra and calculus in Volume 1, geometry and analysis of functions in Volume 2 and discrete mathematics and linear algebra in Volume 3. Each volume is organized along the slightly supplemented SEFI curriculum (Alpers 2014).

Limitations of the SEFI curriculum are discussed in Risse (2023). Students find their way around quickly as every one of the 42 chapter has the same structure: Introduction, Competence List, Problems and Solutions.

Students' Feedback

A survey at the end of 2023 resulted in very positive feedback to the first volume. The statement “The exercises are the most important feature of the book for me” is agreed with by the majority, with a mean of 1.47 on the five-point Likert scale: agree (1) - tend to agree (2) - neutral (3) - tend to disagree (4) - disagree (5). There is also clear agreement with the statement “The competence lists are the perfect introduction to the topic for me”, mean 2.07. In the open questions at the end, a majority emphasize the clarity and structure of the book. One student wrote: “The author uses appropriate examples and formulations to explain difficult issues.” At the same time, more detailed solutions are desired. A student remarked: “In the solution of some exercises more intermediate steps would be helpful for a better understanding.” His wish was reaffirmed by many other student in the discussion of the survey.

Metacognition and Motivation

Orientation is crucial for learning security, i.e. the sureness to have learnt the right material and the certainty to be able to apply what one has learned. Methods as learning maps or advance organizers are helpful to show where a student is now, where the student has been and where the student is going (Asubel 1980). Dealing with the meta-level of the learning material is not particularly captivating for most students, however it is significantly increasing the persistence of what has been learned. The competence list brings the meta-level of the learning material to the fore. Working towards the goal of passing their exams, students make intensive use of the competence lists. Students appreciate the transparency of the examination requirements. Checking off completed learning objectives makes their own progress visible and boosts their motivation.

Further features of the learning environment

A series of videos showing solutions to single exercises was created during Corona lockdown. The learning objectives are mentioned in the introduction to the video. Students expressed their high appreciation of the videos and used them in preparation of the exams. Students develop a personal relationship and receive repeated feedback on tasks in exercises in the “Master-or-Die” format according to the approach of Nölte (2021). Here, a self-selected exercise is worked on to perfection with the help of feedback from the lecturer. Only a complete solution is graded (“Master”). Incomplete or incorrect solutions are not accepted (“Die”). The “Master-or-Die” format follows the ideas of “Mastery Learning” by Bloom (2020).

The possibility to choose topics on their own learning path is extremely motivating for students. A wealth of learning material structured by competence lists opens a wider learning landscape that can be offered for self-organized learning.

Conclusion

Competence lists are an extremely suitable tool for enhancing metacognition of one's own studies. The experience of one's own ability to study is particularly important in undergraduate studies. Competence lists strengthen students' motivation and learning success. The SEFI curriculum provides a good basis for developing the basic engineering mathematics skills. Linking a learning objective with exercises helps students to understand the objectives meaning. Additionally, their own learning success is checked. The “Mathe - kann ich” book series supplements Core 0 and Core 1 of the SEFI curriculum with exercises, i.e. problems and solutions. The combination of working with chapters from the book series, supplementary video material and feedback on completed problem solutions worked excellently in practice.

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